

Organiser Interview Guide for Hybrid Hackathons

This interview guide comprises of a pre-event and post-event instrument, designed to gather perceptions from hybrid hackathon organisers and covering pre-event planning, event execution and post-event retrospectives.

Pre-hackathon Interview Guide

Introduction

"Thank you for participating in this study. The aim is to explore how hybrid hackathons function, identify best practices, and derive suggestions for future event organisers and participants. During this interview, we will discuss your motivations for organising this event as well as your involvement in the planning of the hackathon. We will also discuss the planning process overall with an emphasis on the hybrid format, including technology choices and hybrid space layouts."

Introductory questions

Let's start by talking about why you decided to organise this hybrid hackathon.

- How did you get involved as an organiser?
- How many hackathons have you organised before this one? How many were hybrid?
- How did you decide on a hybrid format instead of a purely in-person or online hackathon? [*probes: cost considerations, accessibility and inclusion, flexibility for attendees, environmental and ethical aspects*]

Preparation and background

Let's talk about how you planned for the hackathon.

- When did you start planning the hackathon? (alternative: When did you get involved in the hackathon planning?)
- Can you walk us through the planning process?
 - Did you consult anyone when preparing for the hackathon?
 - Did you follow any existing guidelines for organising hybrid events? If so, what were they?
- From where do you expect remote participants to join? (timezone, locations)
- What - if anything - did you do to prepare for the hybrid format?
- How can participants reach you? [*probe: in-person or remote?*]

Event logistics

Can you walk me through the event program/agenda?

[Team formation, Idea generation, Set-up]

- How - if at all - do you support team formation?
 - How are you planning to address the needs of participants who might just show up alone, online, or in person?
- How are you planning to guide teams?
 - How are you planning to support hybrid teams? [*probes: technology support*]

[Team Collaboration, Team Project]

- Do you have any materials to share or orientation sessions for the teams we could participate in?
- How do you plan to guide teams in the hackathon? [*probes*]
 - *Are roles like a moderator/leader, note-taker, or presenter suggested to the teams? If so, are resources provided to help teams with any of these roles?*
- How will mentor onboarding work? How are mentors made accessible to both online and in-person participants? [*probes: time slots, dedicated technologies/channels, physical setup*]
- Which - if any - activities outside of teamwork did you plan for participants? [*probes: games, meet-ups, coffee breaks*]
 - How do you consider online participants?
- Can we have a walkthrough of the spaces you will provide for hybrid teams?
 - [**during the walk-through**] Can you describe the arrangements you made in the physical space to support the hybrid format? [*probes: room arrangements, remote whiteboard, projector, speakers, mics*]
 - [**during the walk-through**] What technologies are you using to support the hybrid format? Why?

Closing

Can you share what challenges you might expect with the hybrid format?

- Is there anything else you'd like to add regarding your experience in organizing this hybrid hackathon so far?
- [**if experienced**] What - if any - from your past experience in hybrid hackathons did you implement in this hackathon? Please provide a concrete example if possible.
- [**if experienced**] Can you describe any significant changes you made for this hackathon compared to previous events you organized? [*probes*]
 - *Specifically for the hybrid format? Please provide a concrete example.*
 - *What nudged you to make these changes (if changes were made)?*

Post-hackathon Interview Guide

Introduction

"Thank you again for participating in this study. The aim is to explore how hybrid hackathons function, identify best practices, and derive suggestions for future event organisers and participants. During this interview, we will discuss your impression of how the hackathon event went, the challenges you faced, and any future plans you might have."

Introductory questions

Now that the hackathon is over, can you share your overall impressions of how it went?

- What about the hybrid format? How did that go?

Team - hybrid format

- Which - if any - issues did you become aware of related to the hybrid format during the hackathon? Please think of a concrete example.
 - How did you become aware of these issues?
 - How did you address these issues?
 - How did you ensure that the same issue would not come up again?
- Which - if any - challenges related to the hybrid format were you not able to address?
- Did you interact with any hybrid teams?
 - Which team did you think the hybrid set-up worked very well for? Why was this the case? Please think of a concrete example.
 - Any instances of teams you thought did not manage the hybrid format well? Can you describe from your perspective what you thought the issues were?

Retrospection and closing

- What went well?
- What would you do differently when organizing future hybrid hackathons?
- Reflecting on the entire experience, is there anything else you would like to share or think it's important for future hybrid hackathon organizers to know?
- **[if experienced]** How did participants respond to changes made for this hybrid hackathon compared to previous hybrid hackathons you organized?